

Freshwater Diatoms as Bio-Indicators in Urban Wetlands of Central Gujarat, India

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Abstract: The current study attempts to understand the diatom community structure and their role as bio-indicator in the urban wetlands of central Gujarat. The remarkable variation in the composition and distribution of various diatom species were observed. A total of 26 diatom species distributed among 16 genera, highlights rich biodiversity of the region. Among all, high count of certain diatom species namely *Nitzschia palea*, *N. amphibia*, *N. gracilis*, *Pinnularia biceps*, *Navicula radiosa*, *N. lanceolata*, *N. cryptocephala*, *N. obtusa*, *Gomphonema parvulum*, *G. olivaceum*, *Synedra ulna*, *S. acus*, *Amphora ovalis*, *Eunotia lunaris* and *Stephanodiscus hantzschii* were key indicator diatom species. Only pennate diatoms were present at Manjalpur wetland which is highly polluted and eutrophic in nature. Mesotrophic conditions at Harni wetland and Gotri wetland represented dominance of pollution tolerant species. Bhaily wetland is the least polluted among studied wetlands and showed highest diversity of pollution sensitive diatoms. These results provided insights into the ecological importance of endemic diatoms found in urban ecosystems.

Keywords: Freshwater diatoms, Urban wetlands, Vadodara, Central Gujarat, India

Diatoms are ubiquitous in nature and shows significant morphological diversity in aquatic environment. Their cell size ranges between 5 μm -0.5 mm. They account for approximately 20-25% of oxygen production in the world. They are either planktonic or benthic; occur both in solitary or colonial forms. Community structure of diatoms are specific to each eco-region and significantly varies from pristine to polluted water bodies and this helps in distinguishing oligotrophic from eutrophic water bodies. In the past, the function of diatoms as bio-indicators had been studied in Europe, North America, South Africa and East Asia, but such studies are done in very limited areas of India (Van Dam et al 1994, Blanco et al 2004, Taylor et al 2007a, Cejudo-Figueiras et al 2010, Alakananda et al 2011). Diatom research confirmed their important role in silica cycle and their contribution in other biogeochemical cycles, especially in carbon fixation in the carbon cycle by converting CO_2 into biomass in a large proportion. Diatoms are an important basis of wetland food webs and are referred to as 'algae in glass houses' due to their characteristic siliceous mechanism. They play a key role in ecosystem as primary producer and also support secondary productivity by becoming alternative sustainable source of PUFA (polyunsaturated fatty acid). Hence, they are the major primary producers in all aquatic systems including wetlands (Kale and Karthick 2015).

Urban water bodies exhibit high spatio-temporal variations in temperate and tropical regions that influence the distribution pattern and biodiversity of diatoms. The

wetlands of Central Gujarat are vital ecosystems, providing services such as water for domestic use and moderating atmospheric temperature while balancing biodiversity (Soni and Bhatt 2007, Parikh and Singh 2016). A perusal of literature on central Gujarat shows that earlier work on freshwater diatoms is scanty and mainly focused on marine diatoms (Joshi et al 2019). Notable contribution from this region includes publications of Gandhi (1961, 1967) who had recorded 24 species of freshwater diatoms belonging to 10 genera. However, precise ecological aspects, ionic and nutrient related species variations are yet to be explored in classifying water quality classes for prioritizing more polluted wetlands and identifying indicator species for further environmental management in urban wetlands of Central Gujarat. Vadodara city being the cultural capital of Gujarat harbors great floristic diversity, both in terrestrial and aquatic environments (Rathod et al 2019). But its status quo is urbanized due to rapid development and unplanned anthropogenic activities. Disposal of untreated solid and liquid discharge have amplified pollution level in land and water bodies. Due to high potential of these wetlands as a hotspot of aquatic diversity, this investigation is useful to determine distribution of freshwater diatom flora which will further provide insights on a vast array of ecological and taxonomical studies. Also, help in understanding cosmopolitan- endemism and the relative preference for pristine or polluted waters form the base for developing diatom based indices for water quality monitoring.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Diatom samples were collected from selected urban wetlands from definite sampling sites during November 2018 – April 2019 following guidelines as per standard protocols (Karthick et al 2010). The slides of cleaned diatoms were prepared using Naphrax mountant (ri, 1.74) and the frustules were counted and identified to species level by referring standard literatures (Round 1990, Gandhi 1998, Taylor et al 2007b). During enumeration the dimensions of diatom valve characteristics, like length, width and striae densities in 10 µm were measured for species level identification. Diatom community counts were calculated using OMNIDIA software version 6.0 (Lecoinite et al 1993). This software uses only diatoms for the detection of anthropogenic pollution by calculating Trophic Diatom Index (TDI). The pollution levels of the wetlands have been estimated using TDI using given formula:

$$index = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n a_j s_j v_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n a_j v_j}$$

Where a_j = abundance or proportion of valves of species *j in sample,

s_j = pollution sensitivity (1-5) of species j;

v_j = indicator value (1-3 ; Values of sensitivity (s)

*A diatom cell wall consists of two valves in total (TDI, a user's manual, 2001)

Study area: Vadodara city with a current population of 2.1 million, according to 2010-11 censuses is located at 22° 20' 16.5" N latitude, 73° 13' 07.8" E longitude at an average elevation of 129m above sea level. Vadodara features a

semi-arid climate receiving maximum rainfall during monsoons. It comprises of deep black soil which is very fertile. Vadodara's topography includes a mini river Vishwamitri which dries up in summer and banks of Narmada and Mahi rivers. A large number of interconnected water bodies were created during the dynasty of Maharaja Sayaji Rao Gaikwad making provision for the traditional uses of irrigation, drinking, fishing and washing. The selected urban wetlands are located within the periphery of city namely Harni, Gotri, Manjalpur and Bhaily (Table 1). Of these, Harni and Gotri wetland had recently restored under smart city program by Vadodara Municipal Corporation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Diatom analysis: A total of 26 species belonging to 13 pennate and 3 centric diatoms were observed (Table 2). The dominant genera were *Navicula*, *Gomphonema*, *Nitzschia*, *Synedra*, *Pinnularia*, *Stephanodiscus*, *Amphora* and *Eunotia* in the descending order of relative abundance. Harni wetland was dominated by species of *Navicula*, *Nitzschia* and *Synedra*. In case of Gotri wetland, species of *Pinnularia*, *Stephanodiscus*, *Synedra*, *Navicula*, *Amphora* and *Eunotia* were dominant. While, in the Manjalpur wetland, *Nitzschia*, *Navicula*, *Synedra* and *Gomphonema* were prominent. No centric diatoms were reported here. Bhaily wetland showed a great species diversity of diatoms with the presence of centric diatoms like *Cyclotella*, *Melosira* and *Stephanodiscus*; Pennate diatoms genera such as *Nitzschia*, *Gomphonema*, *Epithemia*, *Cymbella*, *Synedra*, *Fragillaria*, *Navicula*, *Achnanthisidium*, *Rhoicosphenia* and *Surirella*. Majority of forms are solitary and only few colonial. Also, pennate

Table 1. Morphometric details of the urban wetlands

Characteristics	Harni Wetland	Gotri Wetland	Manjalpur Wetland	Bhaily Wetland
Position	22°20'23.5" N 73°13'12.8" E	22°18'52" N 73°08'08" E	22°16'33" N 73°11'54" E	22° 17' 02" N 73° 07' 35" E
Zone	Residential	Residential	Industrial	Residential
Submergence Area	5.38.73 Hectares	1.69.95 Hectares	0.29.18 Hectares	6.5 Hectares
Status	Perennial	Perennial	Perennial	Annual
Observations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restored lake, surrounded by temples, housing societies and state highway Clear water Defined boundary for pedestrians walk Recreational activities like boating and water sports Lower diversity of birds No animal entry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restored lake with central island Surrounded by temple and housing societies Boundary is defined for pedestrian walk area Water discolored due to many anthropogenic activities Flowers, garlands, Rubber footwears, Plastic and polythene bags spotted Harbors good diversity of fishes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surrounded by the Industries and slums Water green in color and eutrophication Foul smell Sewage is discharged No animal activity Very low diversity of fish and birds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forested area with little housing Water is relatively clear Few Plastic and Polythene spotted People washing clothes Animals drink water Greater diversity of birds and fishes Niche of Crocodiles

diatoms had high density as compared to centric diatoms (Singh et al 2010). The Harni wetland is perennial as the water recedes considerably during summers. The lake bed is composed of clay and silica. The absence of sensitive genus *Achnanthes minutissimum* shows the moderate level pollution in the lake. The dominating presence of *Navicula cryptocephala*, *N. obtusa*, *N. radiosa* and *Nitzschia gracilis*, *N. palea*, *N. amphibia* represents excessive organic content in the water. The gradual presence of *Synedra ulna* indicates turbidity of nutrient rich water (Hosmani 2013). Low count of sensitive centric diatoms like *Melosira granulata* and

Cyclotella meneghiana represents low to moderate level of anthropogenic pollution.

Gotri wetland is also perennial and its lake bed is micronutrient rich. The dominance of *Navicula radiosa*, *Amphora ovalis* and *Stephanodiscus hantzschii* explicit the tolerance of pollution levels in water. The large presence of *Pinnularia biceps*, *Eunotia lunaris* and *Synedra acus* illustrates resistance to heavy metal concentration and ionic strength (Jüttner and Ormerod 2010). This wetland support good diversity of fishes and had relatively clear water after lake restoration. The absence of certain centric diatoms like *Cyclotella* and *Melosira* and pennate diatoms such as *Cymbella*, *Epithemia*, *Surirella* and *Fragillaria* points toward moderate pollution in this wetland (Parmar et al 2016). In Manjalpur wetland, presence of high organic pollution shows abundance of pollution tolerant diatoms such as *Gomphonema parvulum*, *G. olivaceum* and *Nitzschia palea* citing poor oxygenation and anthropogenic eutrophication of wetland (Singh et al 2013). The *Synedra ulna* and *Navicula cryptocephala* were common pollution indicators found attached to stones submerged in the water body. Bhaily wetland is less polluted, moderate degradation with low to moderate organic pollution and anthropogenic eutrophication. Few centric diatoms were reported like *Melosira varians*, *Cyclotella stelligera* and *Stephanodiscus hantzschii*. Pennate diatoms like *Navicula lanceolata*, *Synedra ulna*, *Gomphonema gracile* and *Nitzschia amphibia* were present in large number whereas short occurrence of *Cymbella tumida*, *Fragillaria capucina* and *Surirella linearis* shows low organic pollution (Humane et al 2010). This is further supported by presence of pollution sensitive species of *Achnanthes minutissimum*, *Epithemia turgida* and *Rhoicosphenia curvata* (Parmar et al 2016).

Diatom community structure closely followed the pollution increase gradient with species richness, diversity and equitability generally differing among sampling sites, tending to be higher in relatively unpolluted compared to pollute sites (Alaknanda et al 2013). All studied urban wetlands were polluted. However, they varied on the basis of organic pollution, anthropogenic eutrophication and waste discharge into them. The presence of organic pollution in Manjalpur wetland can be linked to cultural eutrophication due to sewage and is not enough to sustain a diverse community. The electrolytic compounds discharged from nearby industries were responsible for the fairly low diatom count.

All the urban wetlands are polluted, according to the Trophic Diatom Index (Table 3) where 0-20 are clean waters, 21-40 mild pollution, 41-60 bad waters, 61-100 severely polluted (Hattikudur et al 2014). Manjalpur wetland is highly

Table 2. Abundance of diatoms belonging to different genera across the urban wetlands

Diatom	Acronym	HW	GW	MW	BW
<i>Achnanthes minutissimum</i> (Kützing) Czarnecki	AMIN				+
<i>Amphora ovalis</i> Kützing	AOVA		+		
<i>Cyclotella meneghiana</i> Kützing	CMEN	+			
<i>C. stelligera</i> (Cleve & Grunow) Van Heurck	CSTE				+
<i>Cymbella tumida</i> (Brébisson) Van Heurck	CTUM				+
<i>Epithemia turgida</i> (Ehrenberg) Kützing	ETUR				+
<i>Eunotia lunaris</i> (Ehrenberg) Grunow	ELUN		+		
<i>Fragillaria capucina</i> Désmazieres	FCAP				+
<i>Gomphonema olivaceum</i> (Lyngbye) Kützing	GOLI			+	
<i>G. gracile</i> Ehrenberg	GGRA				+
<i>G. parvulum</i> (Kützing) Cleve	GPAP			+	
<i>Melosira granulata</i> Ehrenberg	MGRA	+			
<i>M. varians</i> Agardh	MVAR				+
<i>Navicula cryptocephala</i> (Grunow) Cleve	NCRY	+		+	
<i>N. radiosa</i> Kützing	NRAD	+	+		
<i>N. obtusa</i> Smith	NOBT	+			
<i>N. lanceolata</i> Ehrenberg	NLAN				+
<i>Nitzschia amphibia</i> Grunow	NAMP	+			+
<i>N. gracilis</i> Hantzsch	NGRA	+			
<i>N. palea</i> (Kützing) Smith	NPAL	+		+	
<i>Pinnularia biceps</i> Patrick and Reimer	PBIC		+		
<i>Rhoicosphenia curvata</i> (Kützing) Grunow	RCUR				+
<i>Stephanodiscus hantzschii</i> (Grunow)	SHAN		+		+
<i>Surirella linearis</i> Smith	SLIN				+
<i>Synedra acus</i> Kützing	SACU		+		
<i>S. ulna</i> (Nitzsch) Ehrenberg	SULN	+		+	+

'+' = Presence of diatom species in particular wetland
HW = Harni wetland; GW = Gotri wetland; MW = Manjalpur wetland; BW = Bhaily wetland

Table 3. Trophic Diatom Index (TDI) values for the urban wetland samples

Sampling stations	TDI	Anthropogenic eutrophication	Anthropogenic pollution indicator
Harni Wetland	42.6	Moderate	NCRY, NRAD, NOBT, NGRA, NPAL, NAMP, SULN
Gotri Wetland	45.5	Moderate	NRAD, AOVA, SHAN, PBIC, SACU, ELUN
Manjalpur Wetland	72.4	High	GPAR, GOLI, NPAL, SULN, NCRY
Bhaily Wetland	37.8	Low	NLAN, NAMP, GGRA, SULN

polluted with deteriorating water quality with increasing temperature. Hence, trophic state of this wetland is eutrophic in comparison to Harni and Gotri wetlands which may be considered as bad waters. The index value of Bhaily wetland falls under the mild polluted category indicating the rate of conversion of organic matter into carbon dioxide and water by the microorganisms was varying between low and moderate. The level of organic pollution was not detected in this lake.

CONCLUSION

The application of total diatom index depicts that Manjalpur wetland is extremely polluted and eutrophic as compared to Harni and Gotri wetland which are mesotrophic in nature. This is possibly a consequence of industrial effluents and untreated sewage discharged in the former and organic waste disposal in the latter. Bhaily wetland was also mesotrophic and mildly polluted due to the raw discharge from the surrounding households. The species richness of following diatoms *Nitzschia*, *Navicula*, *Gomphonema*, *Amphora*, *Stephanodiscus*, *Pinnularia*, *Synedra* and *Eunotia* in studied water bodies has been attributed to obligate nitrogen heterotrophy and enriched nutrient concentration over other sensitive diatoms. The diatom index is derived mainly on the basis of the distribution of diatom species throughout the period of study. Diatom cells often remain undissolved for a longer duration and hence can serve as important indicators of organic as well as anthropogenic pollution. Thus, diatoms not only serve as an important tool to indicate water quality but also depict endemic diversity precisely by using OMNIDIA software.

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Received 15 October, 2019; Accepted 02 February, 2020